

Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 23 October 2001

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STATEMENT BY THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
23 October 2001

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. On August 6 2001, the Commission reported that agreement had been reached with the IRA on a method to put IRA arms completely and verifiably beyond use. This would be done in such a way as to involve no risk to the public and avoid the possibility of misappropriation by others.
2. We have now witnessed an event - which we regard as significant - in which the IRA has put a quantity of arms completely beyond use. The material in question includes arms, ammunition and explosives.
3. We are satisfied that the arms in question have been dealt with in accordance with the scheme and regulations. We are also satisfied that it would not further the process of putting all arms beyond use were we to provide further details of this event.
4. We will continue our contact with the IRA representative in the pursuit of our mandate.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 23 October 2001

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